

ORBITAL STABILITY OF KINK-TYPE WAVES FOR A DEFOCUSING NONLINEAR SCHRÖDINGER MODEL

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Abstract

In this work we present a detailed proof of orbital stability for a family of kink standing waves solutions for a non-linear Schrödinger equation on defocusing regime, which models several phenomena in Mathematical Physics. The kink waves often called dark solitons in the literature are, in particular, non localized solutions of the model non-vanishing at infinity. The proof we will give is based on the results presented by P. Zhidkov in [1]. The theory is developed taking a specific nonlinearity in order to facilitate reading. However, the prove presented in the particular case can be extended, with minor changes, to a more general context of nonlinearity for the model.

1 Introduction

We are interested in studying the orbital stability of certain types of waves that are solutions to the initial value problem (IVP) of the Nonlinear Schrödinger Equation (NLS):

$$iu_t + u_{xx} + f(|u|^2)u = 0, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}, \quad t > 0, \quad (1)$$

$$u(x, 0) = u_0(x), \quad x \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2)$$

where $u = u(x, t) \in \mathbb{C}$ with $(x, t) \in \mathbb{R}^2$, $f(\cdot)$ being a sufficiently regular real function.

For our analysis we will assume u to be of the standing wave type, that is, $u(x, t) = e^{i\omega t}\phi(x)$. Substituting this function into (1), we arrive at the following ODE $\phi'' - \omega\phi + f(\phi^2)\phi = 0$. The main theorem also assumes that ϕ is a kink with non-negative limits, that is, a solutions that do not vanish at infinity and have limits greater than or equal to zero. Setting $\lim_{x \rightarrow \pm\infty} \phi(x) =: \phi_{\pm}$ it is demonstrated that the necessary and sufficient conditions for the existence of these kinks for NLS are:

1. $\phi_-, \phi_+ \geq 0, \phi_- \neq \phi_+$;
2. $-\omega + f(\phi_{\pm}^2) + 2\phi_{\pm}^2 f'(\phi_{\pm}^2) < 0$;
3. $-\omega\phi_{\pm} + f(\phi_{\pm}^2)\phi_{\pm} = 0$;
4. $-\frac{\omega}{2}\phi_-^2 + U(\phi_-^2) = \frac{\omega}{2}\phi_+^2 + U(\phi_+^2)$;
5. $-\frac{\omega}{2}s^2 + U(s^2) < \frac{\omega}{2}\phi_-^2 + U(\phi_-^2)$ for all $s \in (\phi_-, \phi_+)$;

a classic model that satisfies these properties is the cubic-quintic model, that is, with $f_1(s) = s - s^2$.

For the proof of the theorem to be more instructive for readers who do not yet have an advanced understanding of spectral theory and Sobolev embeddings, we will fix

$$f(s) := f_{\omega}(s) = (\sqrt{s} - 1)(2 - \sqrt{s}) + \omega, \quad \omega \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (3)$$

which, substituting into (2), we can obtain the kink-type solution $\phi(x) = 1 + \tanh\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$.

Then $u_{\omega}(x, t) = e^{i\omega t}\phi(x)$ is a solution of (1) associated with $f = f_{\omega}$ with initial value $u_{\omega}(x, 0) = \phi(x)$.

A suitable functional space to study the dynamics of kink-type solutions for (1) is the so-called Zhidkov spaces, defined as follows:

Definition 1.1. Given $k \in \mathbb{N}$ the space $X^k(\mathbb{R})$ is the closure of the space

$$\left\{ v \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}) \cap C^k(\mathbb{R}), v \text{ is } \hat{A} \text{ absolutely } \hat{A} \text{ continuous } \hat{A} \text{ and } v' \in H^{k-1}(\mathbb{R}) \right\}$$

with respect to the norm $\|v\|_{X^k} = \|v\|_{L^\infty} + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \left\| \frac{d^i v}{dx^i} \right\|_{L^2}$, where $H^{k-1}(\mathbb{R})$ denotes the classical Sobolev space of index $k-1$, based on the space $L^2(\mathbb{R})$.

Now, note that $f_\omega(|z|^2)z$ is not holomorphic, so the classical result of well-posedness for the IVP (1)-(2) presented in [1] does not apply. To solve this problema, we use perturbations of u_ω by functions $\psi(\cdot, t) \in H^1(\mathbb{R})$ and the well-posedness theory developed in [2].

2 Main Results

Now let

$$R(\tau) = \|u(\cdot - \tau, t) - \phi(\cdot)\|_{H^1} \quad (4)$$

and τ_0 such that $R(\tau_0)$ is the minimum value of $R(\tau)$. Finally, we define

Definition 2.1. With τ_0 defined above, we define

$$v(x, t) := u(x - \tau_0, t), \quad (5)$$

$$z(x, t) := |v(x, t)| - \phi(x). \quad (6)$$

Now, let $u \in X^1$ be a solution of (1) such that $u(\cdot, 0) - \phi(x) \in H^1$. Additionally, let z be such that $\|z(\cdot, t)\|_{H^1}$ is small enough so that $0 < \phi(x) + z(x, t) < c < \infty$ for all x , Then we can use the following complex representation of v :

$$v(x, t) = (\phi(x) + z(x, t))e^{i[\omega t + \tilde{\omega}(x, t)]}, \quad (7)$$

where $\tilde{\omega}(x, t)$ is a real absolutely continuous, bounded, and periodic function with period $2\pi m$, $m \in \mathbb{Z}$. Obviously $v \in X^1$ and

$$v_x(x, t) = [\phi'(x) + z_x(x, t) + i(\phi(x) + z(x, t))\tilde{\omega}_x(x, t)]e^{i[\omega t + \tilde{\omega}(x, t)]}. \quad (8)$$

Now, we use the above representations and the following energy functional

$$E(u) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} \left\{ \frac{1}{2}|u_x(x)|^2 - U(|u(x)|^2) + \frac{\omega}{2}|u(x)|^2 + D \right\} dx \quad (9)$$

where $U(s) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^s f(r)dr$ and $D = -\frac{\omega}{2}\phi_-^2 + U(\phi_-^2)$, to prove the main theorem:

Theorem 2.1. Let $f \in C^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$ and suppose that conditions 1-5 are satisfied. Then the kink $u_\omega(x, t) = e^{i\omega t}\phi(x)$ of the NLS (1) is stable in the following sense:

For every $\epsilon > 0$ there exists $\delta > 0$ such that if $u_0 \in X^1$, $|u_0(\cdot)| - \phi(\cdot) \in H^1$, $\|z(\cdot, 0)\|_{H^1} < \delta$ and $\|\tilde{\omega}_x(\cdot, 0)\|_{L^2} < \delta$, then the solution $u(x, t) \in X^1$ of the problem (1)-(2) is global. Moreover,

$$|u(\cdot, t)| - \phi(\cdot) \in H^1, \quad \|z(\cdot, t)\|_{H^1} < \epsilon \quad \text{and} \quad \|\tilde{\omega}_x(\cdot, t)\|_{L^2} < \epsilon, \quad \text{for all } t > 0. \quad (10)$$

References

- [1] Zhidkov, P. E. - *Korteweg-de Vries and Nonlinear Schrödinger Equations: Qualitative Theory*, Springer Berlin, Heidelberg, (2001).
- [2] GALLO, C. - *The Cauchy Problem for Defocusing Nonlinear Schrödinger Equations with Non-Vanishing Initial Data at Infinity*, Communications in Partial Differential Equations, **v.33, n.5**, (2008), 729-771.